

ELECTRIC BICYCLES VERSUS TRADITIONAL MOTORCYCLES: AN IN-DEPTH COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10561270>

ABSTRACT

E-bikes, a rapidly developing hybrid technology, are upending preconceived ideas about conventional, passive, non-motorized recreation. The purpose of this review of the literature is to determine whether electric bikes can take the place of conventional motorcycles. According to a 2018 nationwide research study involving nearly 1,800 new electric bicycle owners, younger individuals tend to utilize e-bikes more frequently for reasons of utility, such as substituting car trips for traveling, errands, and hauling cargo, while elderly people and those with limitations in their mobility use them mostly for wellness and recreation. Through the use of the 100 participants from Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa) cities, the analysis was an independent sample t-test by comparing two different groups of people. Half of the group answered for e-bikes and the rest for traditional motorcycles to determine the performance. Independent sample t-tests have shown that range, power output, battery life and durability, rider experience, safety features, and cost effectiveness don't show any significant difference to the level of performance between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. Conversely, energy efficiency, charging time and overall performance show a significant difference to the level of performance between e-bikes and traditional motorcycles. Based on the results, it has shown that electric bicycles cannot fully replace

traditional motorcycles in some aspects but it can be enhanced and dealt with great interest in changes or development. This is due to the result of having a significant difference on the overall performance which is the variable being tested in the study.

Keywords: *e-bikes, technology, traditional motorcycle, performance, development, substitute*

INTRODUCTION

There are now more brands and models available in the market due to the increasing interest in e-bikes. Both well-established bicycle manufacturers and upstarts have realized the future possibilities of e-bikes and have been creating and introducing their own lines of electric bicycles. As a result of the heightened competition, manufacturers are working to advance battery technology, motor efficiency, design, and overall performance. Technology can be used both inside and outside of outdoor recreation areas and wilderness areas. It not only influences our inclinations toward the environment but also our beliefs about the proper management of wilderness and recreational areas.

Concerns about technology integration in outdoor environments are generally divided into three categories as it becomes more prevalent categories: 1) the quickening pace of technical advancements impacting outdoor activities and their commercialization; 2) the growing number of social repercussions (disagreement, the structure and cultural functions of parks and nature; and 3) the environmental effects (increased erosion and disturbance of wildlife) and social effects (crowding and displacement). Electric-assisted outdoor recreation is one area where innovation is influencing consumer preferences, recreational vehicles, such as electric skateboards, scooters, and bikes. Pedelecs, booster bikes, bicycles with electric motors, power bikes, and other terms for e-bikes are bicycles with a built-in electric motor no more powerful than 750 watts (Nielsen, 2019). Because motorcycles are inherently dangerous, studies on the health and safety of commercial motorcyclists have been conducted in a number of SSA cities. Current data on traffic accidents in certain nations suggests that motorbikes and motor-tricycles continue to have greater fatality rates in metropolitan areas (Peters et al., 2023).

This study's objective was about determining whether electric bicycles can be a replacement for traditional motorcycles by comparing the level of performance of both vehicles. The objective of this study is to determine if electric bicycles can uphold the performance of which has been given by traditional motorcycles to its owners. This is due to the effects of electric bicycles that can be essential to going green and be helpful to the environment. This research may be beneficial to economic, consumer preference and government laws and regulation. The economy may be affected differently by traditional motorcycles and electric bicycles, depending on the consumer and industry. The study may provide light on the financial benefits of switching to electric vehicles. Knowing the difference in performance between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles might help in comprehending consumer interests, an essential aspect for producers and legislators. The researcher's conclusions may influence transportation-related laws and

regulations. To make well-informed decisions about incentives, rules, and growth of infrastructure, governments frequently depend on research.

Research Questions

The purpose of the research is to determine how effectively electric bikes work in Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa) areas as an efficient daily automobile substitute and how acceptable they are thought to be by riders. In order to gather all pertinent data, knowledge, and details, the researchers would want the participants to respond to the following inquiries:

1. What is the respondents' profile like in terms of:
 - 1.1 Location
 - 1.1 Age
2. What's the level of performance of e-bike and traditional motorcycle in terms of:
 - 1.1 Energy efficiency
 - 1.2 Range
 - 1.3 Charging time
 - 1.4 Power output
 - 1.5 Battery life and durability
 - 1.6 Safety Features
3. Is there a significant difference between:
 - 3.1 Electric Bicycles
 - 3.2 Traditional Motorcycles

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The National Capital Region's (NCR) Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa) zone served as the study's location. The participants of the study are the individuals who live nearby, who use E-bike and who use traditional motorcycles. The researchers have chosen these locations as they have conducted an observational study in this location. The researchers have chosen the area as many people are using e-bike in this area. This is due to the fact that there are markets in this area and many prospective respondents are going to the market to buy their needs by using an e-bike and some of them are waiting in line as a means of transportation for those people who need a ride back home. Also, this area is accessible to national highways.

Population and Sampling

The people who utilize traditional motorcycles and electric bicycles because of their effectiveness were considered to be the target demographic in this study. Purposive sampling was the method of sampling that was employed. The researchers chose the study's participants at their own discretion using a method called intentional sampling.

This specific type of non-probability sample is sometimes referred to as a judging or expert sample.

The sampling technique utilized in the study was non-probability, wherein the number of samplings used was through the help of G*power. The researchers chose G*Power as it offers a powerful and incredibly user-friendly way to encourage the use of power analysis in standard statistical data analysis processes. It provides visuals and procedure statement outputs in addition to a broad range of power analysis computations. These people were selected by researchers based on certain characteristics. The researchers utilized this type of sampling technique as the researchers seek for specific criteria to be fulfilled by the participants. Furthermore, the criteria encompass the need for an overall number of one hundred (100) participants consisting of fifty (50) individuals each group ages from 18 to 59 years old. The respondents were people from Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela. Also, these respondents will be divided into two (2) groups with fifty participants each; the first group of participants own an electric bicycle for more than six months and the second group owns a motorcycle for more than six months where they use it whether for work and/or home-errands.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire consists of a prepared list of questions intended to gather data for analysis, research, or other purposes from respondents. This approach is widely employed in social science research, market research, and other domains to methodically gather data from a representative sample of people. Usually, the questionnaire is made up of a number of inquiries covering distinct subjects or passions. The survey questionnaire was validated by professionals, Ms. Sheila Marie DJ. Apostol, MBA, CPM and Mr. Dindo Inso.

1. Google forms

The researchers have conducted the survey using an online survey. These were done by using Google forms to answer the set of questions. In order to gather more respondents, they have chosen this type of survey. By using this type of survey, the researchers have created a poster to call for respondents and joined online groups on social media to gather the participants who have answered the survey. The survey questionnaires included in the Google forms are self-made and were validated by professionals for quality and genuineness. Also, the survey questionnaires were translated to Tagalog through the use of Google translator.

2. Informed Consent

Before answering the questions, the researchers collected the information from the respondents, who were asked for their permission to conduct the survey. The respondents were given an explanation of the study by the researchers through the tool. In order to make sure that those who participated were aware of and were eager to engage in the study, the tool acted as an overview for the researchers. One of the cornerstones of research ethics is informed consent. Its goal is for human subjects to be able to freely (voluntarily) participate in research after being fully informed about the

implications of doing so and having given their agreement in advance (University of Oxford, 2021).

3. Screening Tool

The purpose of screening tools is to identify potential problems before they become serious ones. As a result, they are typically used as the first step in the process of assessment to determine whether a more in-depth evaluation is necessary (Fenley & Langer, 2022). In order to assess the respondents, they were asked to answer certain questions that have allow them to pursue answering the set of questionnaires. Their answers were the basis of the researchers if the answers that they have answered were valid for the paper. This have been used as an evaluation for the researchers.

4. Scale (Likert's Scale)

The psychometric measure known as the Likert scale was created by American social researcher Rensis Likert. Likert made a distinction among a rating system proper, which results from a group of respondents to a collection of variables, together with the rating format for responses along a range. On a balanced 4-point agree-disagree scale, respondents to Likert items indicate how much they are in agreement or disagreement with a series of propositions. Thus, the range expresses their degree of agreement or disagreement with something in particular (Uebersax, 2006).

Scope and Limitations

To get the required information, the researchers gathered 100 respondents who reside in the Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa) Area. To evaluate the e-bike's performance, the researchers have searched for users: (1) who have passed the criteria for those who have answered the questions for the performance of e-bike and (2) who have passed the criteria for those who have answered the questions for the performance of motorcycles. The criteria for those who have answered the questions for the performance of e-bike were (a) riders and owners of e-bike, (b) they must be 18 to 59 years old, (c) the users have been using e-bikes for more than 6 months. The other set of criteria will fall to those who have answered the questions for the performance of traditional motorcycles which were (a) riders and owners of motorcycles, (b) must be 18 to 59 years of age, (c) users have been using motorcycles for more than 6 months. The primary approach of this study was an online survey, in which participants have been asked to complete and respond to a questionnaire based on their experiences. Their responses are important in gathering information to compare the traditional motorcycle and e-bike. The study will not include responses of individuals who did not met the set criteria for the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

1. Mean

The statistical measure known as the "mean" is frequently referred to as the average. It is among the simplest and most widely applied measurements of central tendency. When conducting research, the mean is calculated to produce a single,

representative number that captures the typical or central value of a collection of data points. The mean, which denotes average, is calculated by dividing the total number of data points in a collection by their sum. The mean is a helpful metric for comparing different data sets. But the consequences of severe outcomes could harm this strategy (Frost, 2018). The researchers of the study used mean to determine whichever is higher than the other that has been tested.

2. Standard Deviation

A large standard deviation indicates a large divergence from the mean, while a small variance indicates a narrow distribution around the mean. A metric with relation to the mean is the standard deviation. Determining whether sample measurements indicate reasonable inferences about the population also heavily relies on the standard deviations of these metrics. A set of data points' standard deviation is a measurement of how much the data points vary or are distributed. The amount of deviation from the mean (average) of the data that each data point in a datasets exhibit is measured. Data points that are less than or greater than the standard deviation is thought to be closer to the mean than those that are further from the mean. Its main objective is to measure how much variance or dispersion there is in a data set (Beyer, 2021).

3. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

One well-known statistical analysis software application is called Statistical Package for Social Sciences, or SPSS. Its wide range of features, including addition components and additional programs including Amos and Clementine, together with its intuitive graphical user interface make it one of the more popular tools in contemporary statistical research. SPSS has been widely used in corporate and academic study applications since its development in 1968 (Statistics Solutions, 2023). Users may efficiently input, purge, and manage data using SPSS. Within the software, researchers can arrange and prepare their data for study. To visualize data and show results, the software enables users to build a variety of graphs and charts, including bar charts, scatter plots, histograms, and more. Due to its characteristics for survey design, data collection, and analysis, SPSS is frequently used in survey research and is a preferred tool for social science investigations.

4. Independent Sample T-test

The independent sample t-test is used to determine if there's statistical evidence for an important distinction in the related population means when examining the means of two distinct groups. The Independent Samples t-test is a parametric test. When examining (1) statistical differences between two groups' means, (2) statistical distinctions between the means of two measures, and (3) statistical variances between the means of two change scores, the Independent Samples t Test is frequently employed. Finding out if the samples differ from one another is the aim of this test (National University, 2023).

RESULTS

The data collected by the researchers from the survey using Google form is included in the section of the paper that follows. The gathered data were appropriately

analyzed, presented, and interpreted. Whether an electric bicycle can take the place of a traditional motorcycle depends on the findings.

Demographic Profile

Table 1:

Demographic Profile

Demographic		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Location		
18-59	Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa) area	100	100%

One hundred residents of the Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela areas participated in this study. The selected individuals, whose ages range from 18 to 59, completed the study's 100% sample.

Descriptives

Table 2:

Descriptives' Statistics

Variables	Mean for Electric Bicycles	Mean for Traditional Motorcycles	Standard Deviation for Electric Bicycles	Standard Deviation for Traditional Motorcycles
Energy Efficiency	3.42	2.69	0.64	0.93
Range	3.16	3.41	0.66	0.79
Charging Time	2.76	3.28	0.85	0.90
Power Output	3.12	3.38	0.81	0.88
Battery Life and Durability	3.10	3.40	0.82	0.78
Safety Features	3.06	3.24	0.64	0.87
Performance	3.12	3.42	0.67	0.76
TOTAL	3.10	3.26	0.72	0.84

The table above shows the differences between the means of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles and the overall standard deviation. This includes the six variables as well as the dependent variable which is the performance. In this table, it was seen that the traditional motorcycles got the highest mean score of 3.42 in performance while electric bicycles are higher than traditional motorcycles in terms of energy efficiency with a mean score of 3.42.

Independent Samples T-test

Table 3:

Energy Efficiency

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Energy Efficiency	<0.001	Reject HO1: There are significant differences between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of energy efficiency.

Table 3 indicates the energy efficiency to the performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was <0.001. The retrieved result led to the rejection of null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to reject the null hypothesis if the significance level did not exceed 0.05. It means that there are significant differences in energy efficiency between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. This also means that electric bicycles are more energy efficient than traditional motorcycles when compared to their means where e-bike have a 3.42 score while traditional motorcycles have 2.69.

Table 4:

Range

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Range	0.093	Accept HO2: There are no significant differences between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of range.

Table 4 indicates a range to the performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.093. The retrieved result led to the null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to support the null hypothesis as true if the significance level exceeds 0.05. Therefore, there were no significant differences between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of range. In terms of range, traditional motorcycles have a higher mean score of 3.41 than electric bicycles that have a score of 3.16 where it was seen that there's no significant difference between the two.

Table 5:

Charging Time

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Charging Time	0.004	Reject HO3: There are significant differences between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of charging time.

Table 5 indicates the charging time on performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.004. The retrieved result led to the rejection of null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to

reject the null hypothesis if the significance level did not exceed 0.05. It means that there are significant differences in charging time between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. In this dimension, it was seen that electric bicycles are lower than traditional motorcycles wherein it has a 2.76 score than the score of traditional motorcycles which was 3.48. It means that the owners of traditional motorcycles were more satisfied with the time it consumes when being fueled.

*Table 6:
Power Output*

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Power Output	0.129	Accept HO4: There are no significant differences between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of power output.

Table 6 indicates the power output to the performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.129. The retrieved result led to the null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to support the null hypothesis as true if the significance level exceeds 0.05. Therefore, there was no significant difference between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of power output. It was concluded that electric bicycles have a lower power compared to traditional motorcycles which has a 3.38 score than that of the electric bicycles which was 3.12.

*Table 7:
Battery Life and Durability*

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Battery Life and Durability	0.066	Accept HO5: There is no significant difference between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of battery life and durability.

Table 7 indicates a battery life and durability to the performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.066. The retrieved result led to the null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to support the null hypothesis as true if the significance level exceeds 0.05. Therefore, there was no significant difference between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of battery life and durability. In this dimension, it was concluded that electric bicycles were lower than traditional motorcycles wherein it has a mean score of 3.10 while the latter has 3.40 score.

*Table 8:
Safety Features*

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
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Safety Features	0.243	Accept H07: There is no significant differences between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of safety features.
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Table 8 indicates safety features to the performance level of electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.243. The retrieved result led to the null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to support the null hypothesis as true if the significance level exceeds 0.05. Therefore, there was no significant difference between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of safety features. For this dimension, it was seen that owners were more likely to feel safe with traditional motorcycles as compared to electric bicycles wherein traditional motorcycles have gathered a score of 3.24 while the latter have a score of 3.06.

Table 9:
Performance

Variable	p-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Performance	0.040	Reject H9: There are significant differences between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of overall performance.

The overall performance level is displayed in the above table. The results, which show how the data were interpreted using independent t-test, show that the researchers' p-value was 0.040. The retrieved result led to the rejection of null, in accordance with the selection rule that directs investigators to reject the null hypothesis if the significance level did not exceed 0.05. It means that there is a significance in maintaining a consistent performance between Electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles. For the overall performance, it has been concluded that owners and riders were more satisfied than electric bicycles where it has a 3.12 score compared to the score of traditional motorcycles that was 3.42.

DISCUSSION

The summary of the results and ramifications of the current study, the research output-based on the study's limitations, conclusions, and potential next steps are all covered in detail. One hundred residents of the Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela areas participated in this study. The selected individuals, whose ages range from 18 to 59, completed the study's 100% sample. Based on the results, there were significant differences between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles in terms of energy efficiency, charging time, and overall performance wherein energy efficiency of electric bicycles was higher than traditional motorcycles with a mean score of 3.42. The rationale for the result is that it is an environmentally friendly mode of transportation for the participants based on their responses on the survey made. On the other hand, for the charging time and overall performance, traditional motorcycles were higher than electric bicycles where they got a mean score of 3.28 for charging time and 3.42 for overall performance. This was because the motorcycles have quicker refueled time and they were contented with the time it consumes as well as it had exceeded their expectations

on overall performance. These rationales were based on the responses of the participants who answered to the google form.

Conclusions

This research study examined the effect of energy efficiency, range, charging time, power output, battery life and durability, and safety features on the performance of electric bicycles and traditional bicycles at people residing in Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, Valenzuela (CaMaNaVa). For today's generation, electric bicycles are essential because they also benefit some people. The study's variable, which is energy efficiency, was deemed satisfactory by users when they reached the desired level of performance.

Furthermore, it was found that the five variables that are range, power output, battery life and durability, safety features, and overall performance used in this study did not meet and satisfy other users. This demonstrates that their only satisfaction was with the energy efficiency it provides. Energy efficiency was the variable with the highest mean score of 3.42 and it also has significant difference in the performance level of both vehicles which means that electric bicycles contribute to the betterment of the environment wherein it helps in saving energy. On the other hand, charging time also has a significant difference between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles only that traditional motorcycles have the highest mean score of 3.28 which means that users were more satisfied with the time it consumes to fuel the motorcycle. In terms of the overall performance, both vehicles also have to conclude, electric bicycles still cannot replace traditional motorcycles in terms of range, charging time, power output, battery life and durability, safety features, and its overall performance although there will be developments and areas to enhance the scores of electric bicycles to increase the interests of users in utilizing electric bicycles.

Recommendations

Recommendation in Light of the Results

With the use of six distinct variables, the researchers conducted this study to determine whether electric bicycles can be an alternative to traditional motorcycles. The researchers advise users to investigate the potential of electric bicycles and make use of them as they can provide help in environmental factors such as going green and lessening the pollution caused by traditional vehicles, even though the results indicated that electric bicycles cannot completely replace traditional motorcycles. The study also found that charging time has the lowest mean score, where the researchers recommend to the manufacturers to provide a higher watt for charging adapters so that there would be a faster charging time. The researchers also recommend that users can utilize the charging time to also do other tasks while waiting to be fully charged. The study also found out that the dependent variable which is the performance that also has a significant difference between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles where traditional motorcycles uphold its high level of performance. The researchers recommend that users of traditional motorcycles could consider the capability of an electric bicycle as it also gives a quality.

Furthermore, the Researchers recommend having a collaboration with the manufacturer, forming an alliance with e-bike producers to provide special discounts or promotions for neighborhood residents, encouraging local adaptation. Working together to produce informative workshops or demonstrations that highlight the newest e-bike models and technology, stimulating curiosity and awareness. Arrange test ride events in collaboration with manufacturers so that neighbors can get a firsthand look at e-bikes. Examine the viability of collaborative marketing initiatives to emphasize the neighborhood's dedication to environmentally friendly transportation. Create a feedback loop to exchange needs and preferences within the community, assisting manufacturers in improving their products to better meet regional demands. These would be helpful in spreading knowledge and creating awareness to the benefits of electric bicycles in terms of its effect on the environment when used. The researchers also recommend a community engagement program in using e-bikes. Public Participation thru education programs, to inform the public about the advantages of sustainable transportation, such as lower emissions, better air quality, and improved public health, arrange workshops, seminars, and awareness campaigns.

Establish forums where residents may discuss issues pertaining to transportation, share ideas, and take part in local decision-making. Consequently, the researchers recommended that electric car makers focus on enhancing battery life and durability, power output, safety features, and range. Users can optimize their search for reasonably priced gears that can maintain and increase both the performance and user safety of electric bicycles in order to enhance the level of performance of these vehicles. Thus, maintaining a vehicle on a regular basis may lengthen its longevity.

Additionally, researchers want to recommend ebike for sustainable transportation, to improve safety and accessibility, encourage the construction of e-bike infrastructure, such as designated lanes and charging stations. They also encourage the government to offer subsidies and incentives to e-bike manufacturers so that they can lower their costs and increase usage. To encourage a cultural shift toward sustainable transportation, run public awareness campaigns in your community to inform people about the advantages riding an e-bike has for your health and the environment. To create a smooth and environmentally responsible multi-modal transportation network, work with urban planners and legislators to incorporate e-bikes into the current public transportation systems.

Recommendations for Further Study

During the course of this study, the researchers encountered a few obstacles. One of these is the range of respondents; given the purpose of the study, only residents of the CaMaNaVa area were included in the professional assessment process used to choose the respondents. For this reason, the researchers advise those who wish to carry out this study in the future to do so in-depth, focusing on a population that actually uses and is well-versed in these vehicles. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct ongoing comparative studies between electric bicycles and traditional motorcycles, continuously evaluating and addressing performance gaps. This includes extensive user surveys, real-world performance tests, and in-depth technological evaluations. Additionally, there is a need for long-term studies to gather insightful data important for the advancement of electric bicycle technology. The researchers encourage collaborative research involving universities, e-bike industry partners, and government entities such as the (LTO) Land

Transportation Office and (MMDA) Metropolitan Manila Development Authority. Such collaborations combined expertise and resources, promotes comprehensive analysis and innovative solution development of e-bikes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research paper has undergone ethical compliance through the use of letting the participants agreed to an informed consent and uphold and respect their given rights. The researchers of the study have not done any forceful actions and informed them that the information that they have provided were used solely for the objectives of the paper. The data of the respondents were not disclosed to anyone else and remained confidential in compliance to the Data Privacy Act. They were also given the rights of when they felt any discomfort in answering, they can withdraw from continuing the succeeding sections of the questionnaire and withdraw from participating. Furthermore, the study was conducted without any conflict of interests.

The researchers also avoided plagiarism by citing the authors of related literature used in the study. The paper underwent a plagiarism check where it got twelve (12) over the twenty (20) percent quota for plagiarism of undergraduate courses following the Research Development and Innovation Center's (RDIC) regulations. The paper did not have any bias on the information that have been interpreted for the results where it was purely from the answers of the respondents that have passed and met the criteria for the data gathering.

Acknowledgments

The researchers are first and foremost appreciative of God Almighty for the blessings He has given us while conducting this research. It gave us the tenacity and fortitude we required to conquer every challenge and issue we ran into while studying. Putting our trust in Him made this research even better. The researchers want to express their sincere gratitude to Ms. Marianne A. Iban, our research adviser, for your perseverance, guidance, determination, and knowledge as well as your unwavering support throughout our study and research. Her guidance was quite helpful when conducting the research and writing this paper. She gave us instructions on how to conduct the study and clearly present the results. Being able to work and learn under her direction was a great honor. We would also like to extend our gratitude to Mrs. Arsenia U. Gallardo, our department head for your monetary help that aid in our research publication.

We acknowledge the members of our team as well as our research adviser for their dedication, tolerance, cooperation, and enthusiastic support of our study. They are prepared to assist with this undertaking. They must be present for this study to be conducted. We are appreciative of our beloved families' dedication, intercession, and selflessness in educating and readying us for the challenges that lie ahead. We sincerely thank them for their unwavering spiritual support as we finished this study. We would like to thank the respondents from the CaMaNaVa area for giving their time to complete surveys for our study. Lastly, we would like to express our gratitude to Everyone who has assisted us in completing the research, whether directly or indirectly, and to Our Lady of

Fatima University for the help they provided in carrying out this work and completing the research.

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